

A Study on Consumer-Grade EEG Headsets in BCI Applications

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Abstract—This paper emphasizes the importance of wearable electroencephalogram (EEG) headsets with electrodes and their potential applications, particularly in the specialization of Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs). We aim to contribute to the field of BCIs by providing a short overview of recent literature to identify some usage scenarios for consumer-grade EEG headsets (non-medical editions).

The paper highlights how each scenario requires a specific set of appropriately positioned electrodes. Moreover, it will show different BCI settings that comprehend signal preprocessing of brain cerebral waves, feature extraction, control signals, and classification algorithms. The paper will also discuss several key insights into the practical use of consumer-grade low-cost devices. The proposed study aims to be a helpful starting point for researchers interested in working on consumer-grade EEG headsets for BCI by providing an understanding of the current state-of-the-art limits and challenges and giving hints about what setting are suitable for specific application scenarios.

Index Terms—Brain-Computer Interface, Consumer-Grade EEG Headsets, Wearables, EEG Electrode Placement, Machine Learning, Comparative Study.

I. INTRODUCTION

Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) are pivotal not only for enhancing the quality of life for individuals with impairments [1] but also for enabling various applications that span from gaming and entertainment to education and cognitive buildings control [2], [3]. The importance of BCIs is underscored by the growing interest and research in this field, as highlighted by Roy et al. [4]. In the realm of the Internet of Things (IoT) [5], electroencephalogram (EEG) wearable electrodes-equipped headsets have become valuable tools. This is because headsets enable the integration of brain signals with everyday devices, opening new avenues for interaction and control.

This paper emphasizes the significance of EEG electrodes-equipped headsets and their potential applications, particularly in BCIs. We aim to contribute to the field by providing a study of recent literature to identify usage scenarios for consumer-grade EEG non-medical headsets.

Each scenario necessitates a specific set of electrodes positioned appropriately. By examining various studies, we discuss how different applications require different configurations of electrodes around the human head to acquire suitable brain signals for processing. Moreover, the paper will show different

BCI settings including signal preprocessing of brain cerebral waves, feature extraction, control signals, and classification algorithms. This study will also discuss some key aspects into the practical use of consumer-grade low-cost devices by furnishing helpful considerations about the feasibility, limitations, applicability, and performances obtained by actual BCI systems. Through this work, we aim to demonstrate the potential of consumer-grade headsets in supporting a wide range of BCI applications. This exploration not only underscores the flexibility and capability of such devices but also sets the stage for future research on the exploitability of consumer-friendly BCIs, thereby broadening their usability.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II will introduce the brain signals and how they can be gathered by EEG headsets. Furthermore, it will show how BCI signals can be exploited for the automatic interaction of devices through control commands. Section III will report a study about the state-of-the-art of EEG-based BCI systems explored for research purposes. Section IV will introduce and discuss important aspects involving the practical use of the considered devices. Finally, conclusions will be drawn with an indication of future research directions.

II. BRAIN SIGNALS

A. Brain Cerebral Cortex Map

The brain can be broadly divided into two main parts: the cerebral cortex and the sub-cortical regions¹. Each of these parts plays a crucial role in maintaining various functions necessary for survival and higher-order processing [6].

The sub-cortical regions are located beneath the cerebral cortex and are primarily responsible for controlling the brain's basic and vital functions. These include regulating heart rate, maintaining body temperature, and managing respiration. These regions are also heavily involved in processing emotional responses, such as fear and reflexive actions, which are critical for survival. Moreover, sub-cortical areas are essential for learning and memory, providing the foundational mechanisms that support these cognitive processes. Structures within these regions, such as the thalamus, hypothalamus, amygdala, and hippocampus, play significant roles in these functions. The thalamus acts as a relay station for sensory and motor signals to the cerebral cortex, the hypothalamus regulates homeostasis and endocrine functions, the amygdala

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¹Anatomy of the brain. American Association of Neurological Surgeons. <https://www.aans.org/en/Patients/Neurosurgical-Conditions-and-Treatments/Anatomy-of-the-Brain>. Last seen July 2024

is crucial for emotional processing, and the hippocampus is vital for memory formation and spatial navigation.

In contrast, the cerebral cortex is considered to be evolutionarily newer and represents the largest and most complex part of the brain². This part of the brain is characterized by its intricate structure and vast array of functions. It is divided into several lobes - frontal, parietal, temporal, and occipital - each associated with different aspects of cognitive processing. The frontal lobe is involved in executive functions, such as planning, reasoning, problem-solving, and motor control. The parietal lobe processes sensory information and is essential for spatial orientation and navigation. The temporal lobe is key for auditory processing and language comprehension, while the occipital lobe is primarily responsible for visual processing. The cerebral cortex is the primary focus of most Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) research due to its role in higher-level functions. BCIs aim to decode neural signals from the cortex to control external devices, providing potential applications in medical, communication, and control technologies. Research in this area often focuses on how the cerebral cortex controls sensory and motor processing, as well as complex cognitive tasks. These include language processing, where the brain interprets and generates spoken and written language; pattern recognition, which involves identifying and processing visual and auditory patterns; planning, which is essential for setting and achieving goals; and reasoning, which involves logical thinking and problem-solving. Overall, the cerebral cortex's ability to integrate and process vast amounts of information makes it a crucial area for understanding human cognition and developing advanced technologies that can interface with the brain. Its complexity and importance in higher-order brain functions underscore why it is a central focus in neuroscience and BCI research.

In order to detect brain signals through high-resolution EEG systems, a precise and standardized electrode placement on the scalp is required. Two widely used standard systems for electrode placement are the 10-20 and the 10-10 systems [7], having respectively 21 and 74 electrode positions. Each system offers different detail and spatial resolution levels tailored to varying research and clinical needs. The name of the systems refers to the percentage distances between adjacent electrodes, with respect to the total front-back or left-right distance of the skull. The 10-10 system is particularly useful for more detailed brain mapping and advanced research because of the increasing number of electrodes providing higher spatial resolution. In Figure 1 it is reported the electrode positions on the skull for the 10-10 standard. Table I lists the conventional acronyms of the 10-10 system electrode names, their positions, and the functions of the corresponding area.

Fig. 1: The electrode positions on the scalp of the 10-10 standard.³

B. EEG Detected Brain Signals

The frequency bands of brain signals, recorded through EEG, are divided into various categories, each associated with specific brain activities and mental states. Table II presents a classification of all the EEG bands in terms of frequency and associated mental activities [6], [8], [9]. It can be noted that the progression from low to high EEG frequencies corresponds to a spectrum of mental states ranging from deep sleep and relaxation (Delta and Theta waves) to wakeful alertness and cognitive engagement (Alpha, Beta, and Gamma waves). Each band plays a crucial role in regulating different aspects of brain function and mental activity across various states of consciousness.

C. BCI control signal classification

EEG-based Brain-Computer Interface systems utilize control signals directly derived from the brain activity, with some signals being easier to extract than others, often necessitating additional preprocessing. EEG-based BCI systems focus on identifying changes in brain patterns produced as a response to induced activity (responses to events like sensory stimuli or specific actions) and/or spontaneous activity (ongoing activity without explicit tasks or stimuli). Table III reports the most common classification of control signals used in the EEG-based BCI systems [6].

As a first classification, the control signals directly gathered from the human brain activity are divided into *Event-Related Potentials (ERPs)* and *spontaneous*. Anyway, *other control signals* can be inferred from the EEG but are not directly due to brain activities. A description of such signals follows.

²Brain basics: Know your brain. National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke. <https://www.ninds.nih.gov/health-information/public-education/brain-basics/brain-basics-know-your-brain>. Last seen July 2024

³Wikimedia Commons. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:EEG_10-10_system_with_additional_information.svg. Last seen 09/07/2024.

TABLE I: The 10-10 electrode position standard: names, positions, and functional areas.

Electrodes	Brain Positions	Functions
Fp	Frontopolar	Higher cognitive functions, executive control, planning, and emotional behaviour.
AF	Anterior Frontal	Essential for higher-order cognitive processes, emotional regulation, social interactions, attention, and behavioral control.
F	Frontal	Involved in voluntary movement, executive functions, planning, emotional control, and critical thinking.
FC	Frontocentral	Transition between frontal and central areas, involved in motor functions and planning.
FT	Frontotemporal	Involved in integrating sensory information, language production and comprehension, emotional and social processing, memory functions, auditory processing, and behavioral control.
C	Central	Involved in motor control and sensory perception.
CP	Centro-Parietal	Sensory integration and coordination of sensory information.
P	Parietal	Involved in sensory processing, attention, and spatial perception.
PO	Parieto-Occipital	Transition between parietal and occipital areas, involved in visual and spatial processing.
O	Occipital	Primarily responsible for processing visual information.
T	Temporal	Involved in auditory processing, language comprehension, and memory.
TP	Temporo-Parietal	Involved in sensory integration, language comprehension, memory consolidation, spatial awareness, attention control, social understanding, and motor coordination.

TABLE II: EEG Frequency Bands and Associated Functions

Band	Frequency Range (Hz)	Associated Functions
Delta (δ)	0.5 - 4 Hz	Deep sleep, unconscious states, brain regeneration activity. Dominant in infants and during deep sleep.
Theta (θ)	4 - 7 Hz	Light sleep, dreams, deep relaxation, meditation, drowsiness states. Also associated with creative processes and problem-solving.
Alpha (α)	7 - 13 Hz	Relaxed awake state with eyes closed, light meditation, relaxed wakefulness. Predominant in occipital and parietal regions when a person is relaxed but awake with eyes closed.
Mu (μ)	7 - 13 Hz	Similar to Alpha band in the frequency range, but specific to sensorimotor cortex (C3, Cz, C4 electrodes). "Suppressed" or "desynchronized" during movement or intention to move.
Beta (β)	13 - 30 Hz	Active wakeful state, concentration, intense mental activity, anxiety, tension. Often divided into three sub-bands: Low Beta (13-15 Hz), Mid Beta (15-20 Hz), and High Beta (20-30 Hz). Found in frontal and parietal lobes.
Gamma (γ)	30 - 100 Hz	Higher cognitive functions, integrated sensory perception, focused attention, learning and memory. Binds diverse neurons during simultaneous brain information processing. Optimal levels associated with good memory. Deficiencies linked to learning disabilities.

ERP signals. ERPs refer to the signals generated unconsciously by the subject when she/he receives external sensory stimuli. The ERPs can be further divided into SSEP and P300.

Steady State Evoked Potentials (SSEP) are brain signals matching the frequency of periodic stimuli, such as flickering images, modulated sounds, or tactile vibrations. One of the most used SSEP signals is the Steady-State Visual Evoked Potential (SSVEP), generated in the visual cortex at the same frequency as the flickering image (typically between 6 and 30 Hz) or as integer multiples of the fundamental frequency used as visual stimuli. This allows distinguishing among numerous distinct commands depending on the specific stimuli's flickering frequencies. One common application of SSVEPs is in graphical user interfaces featuring buttons, each associated with a specific frequency. When a subject focuses on one of these buttons, the brain generates a corresponding frequency that can be used, for example, to control the button click.

P300 [10] is an EEG signal that typically emerges approximately 300 ms after a subject is exposed to an unexpected or rare task. This signal is commonly elicited using an "odd-ball" paradigm, where the subject is instructed to focus on a sequence of stimuli in which one occurs less frequently than the others. When this infrequent stimulus

is relevant to the subject, it triggers the P300 EEG signal. The P300 response is predominantly observed in the parietal, frontal, and central lobes along the mid-line of the brain. One of the first P300-based BCI systems was developed for a word-spelling application controlled by brain signals [11], [12]: a letter matrix is displayed on a screen, with each letter flashing in a random sequence. When the letter the user is focused on is highlighted, the user's gaze triggers a P300 signal which is then used for making the selection.

Spontaneous signals. Spontaneous signals are generated voluntarily by the subject without any external stimuli. They are divided into SCP and ERD/ERS.

Slow Cortical Potentials (SCPs) are EEG signals characterized by frequencies below 1 Hz. These low-frequency potentials are typically observed in the frontal and central regions of the cortex. SCPs are not preferred in BCI systems because they are characterized by very slow variations that may last from milliseconds to several seconds.

Event-Related Desynchronization/Synchronization (ERD/ERS) refers to changes in the amplitude of ongoing EEG oscillations at a specific frequency in response to mental commands. ERD/ERS signals are divided into two subcategories: (i) Motor and sensorimotor, and (ii) Mental cognitive signals. Motor and sensorimotor signals are related to motor actions such as moving arms. These signals come

TABLE III: EEG-based BCI Control Signal Classification

ERP	SSEP	
	P300	
SPONTANEOUS	SCP	
	ERD/ERS	Motor and sensorimotor
		Mental cognitive

TABLE IV: Comparison of EEG Devices

EEG Device	# Channels	Electrodes
EMOTIV EPOC X	14	AF3, F7, F3, FC5, T7, P7, O1, O2, P8, T8, FC6, F4, F8, AF4
EMOTIV INSIGHT	5	AF3, AF4, T7, T8, Pz
INTERAXON MUSE 2	4	TP9, AF7, AF8, TP10
BITBRAIN DIADEM	12	Fp1, Fp2, AF7, AF8, F3, F4, P3, P4, PO7, PO8, O1, O2

from over the motor cortex with frequencies located at μ and β bands. These signals are generated in two conditions: the real movement of the body and the mental movement intention (motor imagery). Mental cognitive signals are generated during many tasks, such as music imagination, visual counting, mental rotation, and mathematical computation.

Other control signals. Another specific signal pattern recognized in EEG signals and used in BCI systems is represented by the eye-blink signal. It is largely due to the electrical activity of the facial muscles around the eyes rather than direct neuronal activity in the brain, so it is typically interpreted as a muscular movement rather than a mental command directly derived from EEG brain signals. In some BCI applications, eye-blink signals are treated as artifacts to be removed, but in other applications, they can be used as triggers or commands within the system in order to perform actions or selections.

III. EEG CONSUMER-GRADE HEADSETS BCI APPLICATIONS

This section reports a study about the state-of-the-art of EEG-based BCI systems introduced for research purposes that employ non-medical low-cost EEG acquisition devices. For this purpose, we analyzed a selection of representative papers.

From the selected papers, the most used commercial EEG devices resulted in Emotiv EPOC X⁴, Emotiv Insight⁵, and InteraXon Muse 2⁶. The above devices use a reduced number of electrodes (from 4 to 14) compared to the total electrode number present in the 10-10 system. Another consumer-grade device recently available is the Bitbrain Diadem⁷, which is indeed mainly employed in passive BCI applications such as neuromarketing, neurocinematics, neuroeducation, sleep monitoring, sensorial evaluation, driver vigilance detection, and human factor evaluation. The aim is to decode the user's mental states, such as emotions, mental workload, and

⁴Emotiv EPOC X. <https://www.emotiv.com/products/epoc-x>. July 2024

⁵Emotiv Insight. <https://www.emotiv.com/products/insight>. July 2024

⁶InteraXon Muse 2. <https://choosemuse.com/products/muse-2>. July 2024

⁷BitBrain Diadem. <https://www.bitbrain.com/neurotechnology-products/dry-ceg/diadem>. July 2024

attention [13]. Table IV shows the details about the electrodes hosted in these devices. It is worth noting that the C3, Cz and C4 electrode positions, which are the optimal ones for ERD/ERS motor and mental imagery tasks (see Table I), are not present in these low-cost EEG acquisition devices. For this reason, research studies that use these devices for this kind of application fields need to acquire the motor and mental imagery information by re-elaborating the signals coming from the other available electrodes [14].

Table V classifies the selected papers with respect to the employed BCI control signals. In addition, the table reports the details about (i) the specific applications considered in the papers, (ii) the type of commands activated by the EEG signals in the considered BCI system, (iii) the used electrodes, (iv) the extracted features, (v) the EEG raw signal preprocessing, and (vi) the classification algorithms used to identify the commands. In the following, the selected papers will be discussed in more detail.

The papers [14]–[19] use the spontaneous signals detected through the ERD/ERS paradigm for both general purpose applications and specific ones, like home automation and gaming, by recognizing motor and mental imagery commands. In [14], the Emotiv EPOC+ headset (a previous version of the actual EPOC X) was used to detect the *Left*, *Right*, *Push*, and *Pull* mental imagery commands with the main task of searching the configuration map setting with the minimum number of electrodes that guarantees optimal performances. Here, four features are extracted from EEG signals, namely Band Power (BP), Approximate Entropy (ApEn), statistical features, and wavelet-based features. For classification, Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) are used. The authors state that it is possible to reach an average cross-validation accuracy of 98.55% by using only FC5, FC6, AF3, and AF4 electrodes with the BP and ApEn features and the KNN classification algorithm. In [15], the authors proposed an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) optimization of the EEG signals preprocessed by a low-pass filter with different cutoffs (i.e., $fc_1 = 4\text{Hz}$ and $fc_2 = 15\text{Hz}$) aimed at leg motor imagery recognition. The authors demonstrated that the filtration of high-frequency spectral components significantly enhances the classification performance (up to $90 \pm 5\%$ accuracy) by using only the 8 electrodes Fpz, Fp1, Fp2, Fz, F3, F4, F7, and F8. In [16], the authors propose a BCI-based smart-home interface that leverages motor imagery signals to control home devices in real time. Experiments were tested using the Emotiv EPOC X headset to switch a light bulb on/off or set a dimmer. The three main stages of the proposed BCI system are the preprocessing filtering (a 5th-order Butterworth band-pass filter in the range of 8–30 Hz), the application of a Regularized Common Spatial Pattern (RCSP) filter, and the final classification performed by a Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) classifier. In [17], a 3D BCI-controlled game is developed by using the Muse 2 Headband for the recognition of three different mental states (left and right motor imagery and eye blink); the goal of the game is to collect as many coins as possible. A classification accuracy

of 94.86% is reached when the LDA classifier is used to process the EEG signals after the application of a Butterworth band-pass preprocessing filter at 8-40 Hz and the measurement of the energy of the different frequency bands (Alpha, Beta 1, Beta 2, Gamma 1, Gamma 2). In [18], the Muse 2 Headband was used to test Logistic Regression (LR), and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA) for the classification of eight motor imagery (forward, backward, left, right) and mental imagery (hungry, food, water, sleep) tasks. The features are extracted in the form of absolute band powers, based on the logarithm of the Power Spectral Density (PSD) from the EEG data. The average accuracy achieved by the classifier is 72.5% and 74.7% for LR and QDA, respectively. In [19], the authors propose a compact Convolutional Transformer, named EEG Conformer, to encapsulate local and global features in a unified EEG classification framework, including a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), a self-attention Transformer, and a simple fully-connected layer classifier. The experiments were conducted by using three public datasets in EEG-based motor imagery (the imagination of moving left hand, right hand, both feet, and tongue) and emotion (positive, neutral, and negative emotions) recognition paradigms without the adoption of an EEG headset device.

As regards the ERP signals, the paper [20] uses the SSVEP paradigm for drone control while [21] uses the P300 paradigm for a wheelchair control system. The drone control system in [20] uses only one electrode (Oz) for EEG signal acquisition in order to detect SSVEP signals generated by using a control visual flash stimulus at different frequencies (i.e., 15Hz for forward, 17Hz for backward, 19Hz for left turn, 21Hz for right turn, 25Hz for rise, and 27Hz for fall). The authors use the NI Labview software to perform filtering and threshold calculations of the EEG-detected signal. The value of the threshold is used to control the drone's actions. The accuracy of the control command classification is 90.04%. In [21], the authors propose a P300-based threshold-free brain switch design with the Emotiv Insight headset used to generate a start/stop command for an intelligent wheelchair equipped with an autonomous navigation system. The EEG signals were preprocessed by a band-pass filter (0.5-30 Hz), normalized to an interval of [-1, +1], and classified by two Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifiers.

The eye-blink paradigm was used by [22] and [23] for, respectively, IoT devices and wheelchair control. More in particular, [22] proposes a system based on the use of the Muse-Headband sensor that captures EEG signals when a person blinks. The EEG signals are preprocessed by a 5th order Butterworth filter, with a cutoff frequency of 2 Hz and a sampling frequency of 256 Hz, and then classified into short and long blinks by using the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm with K = 5. The classified blinks are then used to form control commands sent to a cloud server responsible for sending the control action to the connected IoT devices. The accuracy of the classifier is 99.53%. The paper in [23] introduces a real-time control system for disabled electric wheelchairs leveraging EEG signals acquired by the Emotiv

Insight headset. The main goal is to increase the accuracy rate of the brain control system by using an artificial neural network. The complete EEG signal processing flow used for classification includes: the preprocessing with band-pass filter, Hann Windowing and Fast Fourier Transform; the feature extraction of power, recursive energy efficiency (REE), root mean square and logarithmic REE with Discrete Wavelet Transform; the classification with the neural network. The test uses only two electrodes (AF3 and AF4) in order to classify the following commands related to eye-blinking: move forward (left and right eyes blinking together twice), turn left (left eye blinking), turn right (right eye blinking), stop the wheelchair (left and right eyes blinking together once).

In [13] the authors have studied the consumer EEG devices in order to propose the best EEG electrodes configuration settings for the design of EEG headsets specialized for specific tasks: emotion, attention and general purpose. The authors propose different settings based on 2, 4, 6, and 8 electrodes depending on the performance requested by the target application. In order to find the best settings, the experiments were conducted by using public emotion and attention datasets. The preprocessing was made with a band-pass filter at cut-off frequencies of 1 and 55 Hz, and artifact removal. The algorithms used for the classification were SVM and LDA/Decision Tree (DT).

IV. DISCUSSION

Based on the above-written study, we can suggest several key insights into the practical use of consumer-grade non-medical low-cost devices:

Feasibility for Various BCI Applications. Consumer-grade EEG headsets, such as the Emotiv EPOC X, Emotiv Insight, InteraXon Muse 2, and Bitbrain Diadem, can be effectively used for a wide range of BCI applications. These devices offer a more accessible entry point for researchers and developers due to their affordability and ease of use.

Limitations for Motor Tasks. Despite their versatility, these commercial EEG headsets often fall short in applications requiring precise motor control. The absence of critical electrodes at positions like C3, Cz, and C4, which are essential for ERD/ERS-based motor imagery tasks, limits their effectiveness. This gap necessitates the use of alternative electrodes, signal reprocessing, and data fusion [24] techniques to infer the necessary data.

Electrode Requirements. Many BCI applications do not require the full array of electrodes typically available in medical-grade systems. For specific applications, a subset of strategically placed electrodes can suffice. For instance, as demonstrated in various studies, effective BCI performance can be achieved with as few as 1-8 electrodes, depending on the target application [15], [16]. This finding highlights the importance of designing application-specific EEG headsets that balance the number of electrodes with performance needs.

TABLE V: Overview of EEG-Based BCI Research

BCI control signals	Article	Year	Applications	Supported Commands	Used Electrodes	Extracted Features	EEG Signal Preprocessing	Algorithms
ERD/ERS	[14]	2020	Mental imagery recognition	Left, Right, Push and Pull	Various combinations: {FC5, FC6, P7, P8, AF3, AF4}; {FC5, FC6, AF3, AF4}; {P7, P8, AF3, AF4}	Band Power (BP), Approximate Entropy (ApEn), statistical features, and wavelet-based features	Artifact removal	DT, RF, SVM, KNN
	[15]	2018	Leg motor imagery recognition	Movement of left/right leg	Fp2, Fp1, Fp2, Fz, F3, F4, F7, F8	Difference between the values of wavelet energy associated with right leg and left leg motor imagery	low-pass filter with cut-offs at $f_{c1} = 4\text{Hz}$ and $f_{c2} = 15\text{Hz}$	RBF, MLP, SVM-RBF with nonlinear kernel based on radial basis function LDA
	[16]	2023	Motor imagery recognition for Home Automation	Two mental states: imagery right-hand and left-hand movements	AF3, F3, F7, FC5, T7, P7, O1 (Left side); AF4, F4, F8, FC6, T8, P8, O2 (Right side)	-	Band-pass filter; RCSP filter	LDA
SSVEP	[17]	2022	Gaming	Left/right motor imagery and eye blink	TP9, AF7, AF8 and TP10	Energy of each band	Butterworth band-pass filter 8-40 Hz; Time-windows extraction; Split into 5 frequency bands	LDA
	[18]	2020	Motor Imagery and Mental Imagery tasks recognition	Eight cognitive imagery tasks: forward, backward, left, right, hungry, food, water, sleep	TP9, AF7, AF8 and TP10	Absolute band powers for each channel, based on the logarithm of the PSD values	Notch filter (50-60 Hz) to filter out the power noise; Artifact removal	LR, QDA
	[19]	2023	Motor imagery and emotion recognition	Left hand, right hand, both feet, tongue	Dataset 1: 22 electrodes Dataset 2: C3, Cz, C4 Dataset 3: 62 electrodes	-	Band-pass filter; Z-score standardization; Data Augmentation	CNN and Transformer
P300	[20]	2021	Device control (drone)	Forward, backward, left turn, right turn, rise, fall	Oz	SSVEP	-	Matched filter detector
	[21]	2017	Wheelchair control system	Start/Stop	Fz, Cz, P3, Pz, P4, PO7, PO8, Oz	P300 feature vectors	Band-pass filter (0.5-30 Hz) and normalization ([-1, +1] interval)	Two SVMs
EYE-BLINK	[22]	2021	Person blinks detection for IoT devices controlling	Short blinks, long blinks, no blinks	TP9, AF7, AF8 and TP10	-	EEG envelope	KNN
	[23]	2022	Wheelchair control system	Forward, stop, right and left	Various combinations: {AF3, AF4, T7, Pz, T8}; {AF3, AF4}	Power, Recursive Energy Efficiency (REE), Root Mean Square, and Logarithmic REE; all extracted through Discrete Wavelet Transform	Band-pass filter; Hann Windowing; Fast Fourier Transform	ANN
OTHER	[13]	2020	Emotion, Attention, General-purpose	-	AF3, AF4, FC1, FC2, P3, P4, O1, O2, AF3, AF4, C3, C4, PO3, PO4, P7, P8	Power spectral density (PSD), differential asymmetry (DASM), rational asymmetry (RASMM), Hjorth parameters (HP), Shannon entropy (SE), Hurst exponent (HE), Kolmogorov complexity (KC), higher-order cumulants (HOC), and common spatial pattern (CSP)	Band-pass filter; Artifact removal (Eye-blink rejection)	SVM, LDA, DT

User Accessibility and Expertise. The current state-of-the-art in consumer-grade EEG devices allow researchers without extensive neuroscience expertise to engage in BCI research. This fosters interdisciplinary collaboration, particularly involving computer science researchers, who can contribute significantly to the development and optimization of BCI systems [13].

Diverse BCI Applications. This study indicates that consumer-grade EEG headsets are being utilized in a variety of innovative applications. From drone and wheelchair control using SSVEP and P300 paradigms [20], [21] to smart-home interfaces and gaming through ERD/ERS paradigms [16], the versatility of these devices is evident. Additionally, eye-blink detection for IoT device control and wheelchair navigation further showcases the practical applications of these headsets in enhancing user interaction and accessibility [22], [23].

Performance and Accuracy. While consumer-grade EEG headsets have demonstrated commendable performance in various studies, achieving high classification accuracy remains a challenge in some applications. Advanced signal processing techniques, feature extraction methods, and machine learning algorithms play a crucial role in improving the accuracy of BCI systems. The use of specific techniques has shown promising results in enhancing the reliability of these systems [14], [17]. Anyway, it is worth noting that many newer AI algorithms can still be investigated in this field as future research, and there is still room to achieve even better performances.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper has highlighted the importance and versatility of EEG electrodes-equipped wearable headsets in various BCI applications. By reviewing recent literature and examining different studies, we have provided an overview of how different applications necessitate specific configurations of electrodes positioned around the human head to acquire suitable brain signals. Moreover, the paper has shown different BCI settings that comprehend signal preprocessing of brain cerebral waves, feature extraction, control signals, and classification algorithms. Furthermore, several key insights into the practical use of consumer-grade low-cost devices have been discussed in this work.

Our analysis shows that not all BCI applications can be successfully realized with consumer-grade EEG headsets. While these devices offer significant potential and flexibility, they also have limitations. Despite these limitations, consumer-grade headsets proved to be effective for a wide range of applications, particularly when combined with advanced signal processing techniques and machine learning algorithms.

Artificial intelligence offers a promising avenue for overcoming some of the limitations associated with consumer-grade EEG devices. AI can potentially infer brain signals related to certain tasks even when direct measurements are not

available. This approach is used, for instance, in [14], where the lack of electrodes in the central brain region (optimal for ERD/ERS motor and mental imagery tasks) is addressed by reprocessing signals from other available electrodes using machine learning algorithms. This represents an area for future research, where the integration of AI with EEG headsets could enhance their functionality and broaden their applicability in BCI applications.

Future works can also focus on the development of real-time processing algorithms that can handle the data from consumer-grade EEG devices more efficiently, providing immediate feedback and control for various applications, and optimizing headset utilization by conducting in-depth research into specific application areas such as gaming, smart home control, and assisted living technologies. Actually, research in this area focuses on developing lightweight machine learning algorithms that require fewer computational resources and power consumption, making them suitable for embedding on Edge devices (as seen in [25] and [26]), and on optimizing EEG signal processing on customizable hardware like FPGAs [27].

Finally, other research efforts will be focused on the development of novel algorithms for EEG-based BCI applications. Nowadays, regarding machine learning algorithms adopted in this field, research is particularly active in developing new neural network architectures, many of which are proposed as CNN variants [19], [28], [29], while others are based on different models, such as Graph Neural Networks as discussed in [30]. Additionally, deep learning (DL)-based methods require a significant amount of EEG data to avoid overfitting. Consequently, research efforts are also focused on developing new data augmentation techniques, as proposed in [29], [31]–[34].

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